

possessing a methoxyl at C-5 (IIIa). Thus the activation energy of $\overline{S_N^2}$ substitution process by the weak nucleophile acetate ion is high enough to inhibit the reaction in the latter compounds.

We find that the bromine in compounds (III), (V) and (VII) is displaced to the extent of about 70% when the extremely polar solvent DMSO is used as the reaction medium. Thus the reaction of DMSO may be regarded as proceeding by $\overline{S_N^1}$ mechanism probably through the carbonium ion-bromide ion pair⁴.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Acetoxy-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one (IV): A mixture of 2-bromo-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one² (III) (1 g.) and fused sodium acetate (0.8 g.) in DMSO (25 ml.) was heated on a steam bath for 1.25 hr. and then poured into ice-water. Extraction with benzene followed by chromatography of the benzene extract through a column of Brockmann alumina and subsequent evaporation of the solvent furnished a residue. It was crystallised from methanol to yield pure (IV), as colorless needles (0.65 g.; 72.7%), m.p. 142–143°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen prepared earlier by a different route.²

4,5-Dimethoxyindan-1-one: The literature method⁵ was modified as follows: A mixture of 2,3-dimethoxy- β -phenyl propionic acid⁶ (12 g.) and PPA [from P_2O_5 (60 g.) + H_3PO_4 (d, 1.75; 36 ml.)] was held at 103–104° for 10 min. when the mixture turned deep red. It was immediately poured into ice-water and the solid that separated was filtered and washed with water. It was triturated with 20% aq. NaOH, filtered, washed and dried. Crystallisation from light petroleum (b.p. 60–80°) furnished the pure indanone as rectangular prisms (9 g.), m.p. 74–75° (lit.⁵ m.p. 74–75°). The mother liquor on working up afforded an additional quantity of indanone (1 g.). Total yield 10 g., (92.6%).

2-Bromo-4,5-dimethoxyindan-1-one (V): This was prepared by adopting the procedure recommended by Fort⁷. A mixture of 4,5-dimethoxyindan-1-one (5 g.) in methanol (30 ml.) and cupric bromide (12.3 g.) and KBr (7.3 g.) in water (30 ml.) was refluxed on a steam bath for 1.25 hr., poured into ice-water and the precipitate filtered. It was triturated with

3. C.f. H. Gilman, *Organic Chemistry*, Vol. III, J. Wiley and Sons, 1953, p. 35, ref. 107.
4. D. J. Cram and G. S. Hammond, *Organic Chemistry*, McGraw Hill, 1959, p. 244.
5. J. Koo, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 1891.
6. R. D. Haworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2281.
7. A. W. Fort, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 765.

saturated aq. KBr, filtered and washed with saturated aq. KBr and water. The solid was extracted with chloroform (30 ml. \times 3), the extract dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent evaporated. The residue was crystallised from methanol to give pure (V) as colorless rectangular rods (4.7 g.; 65.2%), m.p. 100–101°. Found: Br, 31.0. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_3\text{Br}$ requires Br, 30.77%.

2-Acetoxy-4,5-dimethoxyindan-1-one (VI): A mixture of the bromo compound (V) (1 g.) and fused sodium acetate (0.8 g.) in DMSO (24 ml.) was heated on a steam bath for 1 hr. and worked up as detailed in the preparation of (IV) to afford a solid. It was crystallised from boiling water to give the acetoxy compound (VI) as colorless needles (0.6 g.; 67.1%), m.p. 88–89°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen (m.p. 87.88°) prepared by a different route.⁸

2-Bromo-5-methoxyindan-1-one (VII): A mixture of 5-methoxyindan-1-one⁹ (3 g.) in methanol (50 ml.) and cupric bromide (8.7 g.) and KBr (4.6 g.) in water (20 ml.) was refluxed on a steam bath for 45 min., and worked up as detailed in the preparation of (V). The solid that was obtained was crystallised from isopropanol to afford (VII) as colorless needles (3.2 g. 71.7%), m.p. 96–97°. Found, Br, 33.5. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{Br}$ requires Br, 33.2%.

2-Acetoxy-5-methoxyindan-1-one (VIII): A mixture of the bromo compound (VII) (2 g.) and fused sodium acetate (1.5 g.) in DMSO (80 ml.) was heated on a steam bath for 50 min., and worked up as detailed in the preparation of (IV) to afford a solid. It was crystallised from methanol to give the acetoxy compound (VIII) as colorless needles (1.3 g., 71.4%), m.p. 78–79°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen prepared by a different route.⁸

Chemical Laboratory,
Bihar University,
L. S. College, Muzaffarpur.

Received November 18, 1968

8. N. K. Bose and D. N. Chaudhury, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 411.

9. D. Mukhopadhyay and D. N. Chaudhury, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 433.